

Time-dependency of flexural properties in biaxially oriented polypropylene laminates

Anna Kandinskaia, Pauline Koslowski, Laurens van Audenaerde, Larissa Gorbatikh, Ignaas Verpoest, Yentl Swolfs

State of the art

Problem statement

Results

Conclusions

ORIENTED POLYMERS

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graph TD; A[ORIENTED POLYMERS] --> B[Uniaxial orientation]; A --> C[Biaxial orientation];
```

Uniaxial orientation

- ⊕ High properties along **ONE** direction
- ⊖ **Large** property **GAPS** between the stretched and not stretched directions

Biaxial orientation

- ⊕ Good properties along **TWO** directions
- ⊕ **Limited** property **GAPS** between the two directions

BIAXIALLY ORIENTED POLYPROPYLENE (BOPP)

Simultaneous or sequential stretching:

- Molecular orientation changes
- Crystallinity degree changes
 - Melting point changes

TIME-DEPENDENCY ANALYSIS

EXPERIMENTAL PART

BOPP laminate level

Materials

BOPP films

Hot compaction

125°C

60 seconds dwell time

39 bar

Characterization
at different time
slots

3-point bending test

Drop weight impact test

Differential Scanning Calorimetry

Suitcase shell level

Materials

Characterization
at different time
slots

3-point bending test

Tensile test

Annealing at 40°C and 60°C

Differential Scanning Calorimetry

Three-point bending test results

Laminate level

Suitcase level

Three-point bending test results

Gaps between timeslots statistically analyzed

Laminate level

MD: No significant difference

TD: +30% in 3 months

Stabilization between 1 week and 1 month

Suitcase level

MD: +68% in 1 month

TD: +60% in 1 month

Slower stabilization

Influence of storage condition

Influence of thermoforming process

Three-point bending test results

Gaps between timeslots statistically analyzed

Laminate level

MD: +18% in 3 months

TD: +21% in 3 months

Stabilization between 1 week and 1 month

Suitcase level

MD: +43% in 1 month

TD: +28% in 1 month

Slower stabilization

Influence of storage condition

Influence of thermoforming process

MD = Machine Direction; TD = Transverse Direction

Annealing treatment – suitcase level

DSC analysis

Laminate level

- No change in crystalline phase
- Amorphous phase is responsible of mechanical properties time-dependency

Suitcase level

- Crystallinity change between 1 Day - 1 Week

Impact test results – laminate level

Impact tests can be performed at any time after the production

Tensile test results – suitcase level

Machine Direction

Transverse Direction

Gaps between timeslots statistically analyzed

No significant gaps

Elastic modulus

Failure stress

Failure strain

Significant gap between 1 week and 1 month

Yield point

Resilience

No enough data points between 0.1% - 0.3% of the strain

Cutting process

CONCLUSIONS

Time-dependency analysis

Laminate level

Impact resistance is **NOT AFFECTED** by time

Flexural properties are **TIME-DEPENDENT**

Suitcase level

Crystallinity degree is **NOT AFFECTED** by time

Flexural properties are **TIME-DEPENDENT**

Annealing

Temperature does **NOT ACCELERATE** the time-dependency behavior

Ideal testing time: **ANYTIME**

BETWEEN ONE WEEK AND ONE MONTH

Ideal **Samsonite** testing time:
AT LEAST AFTER ONE MONTH

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Anna Kandinskaia, Arianna Tavano, Pauline Koslowski, Laurens van Audenaerde,
Nathan Vanden Bulcke, Yentl Swolfs

